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Inside INFRA-ART

Newsletter #06 | June 2026

Welcome to the June 2026 edition of the INFRA-ART newsletter!

The past months have brought significant progress across the INFRA-ART data service, including new platform features, expanded data collections, important milestones in our FAIR journey, and new collaborations. In this issue, we share an overview of the latest developments and activities from the INFRA-ART community. Enjoy reading!

~ the INFRA-ART Team

Latest platform updates

New collection: Composite samples

As part of our ongoing efforts to expand reference data collections relevant for heritage science research, we have introduced a new sample category: Composite samples. The collection currently includes 200 mock-up samples designed to replicate the layered structures and material combinations commonly found in works of art. These samples enable the systematic study of pigment and pigment–binder interactions, as well as the influence of preparatory layers and substrates on the resulting spectral fingerprint. Each mock-up sample is linked to its corresponding reference materials, facilitating comparison between complex layered systems and their individual components. [Explore the collection](#)

Spectra data now available for download

Spectral data files can now be downloaded directly from their corresponding sample pages. This update supports our commitment to open science and FAIR data by simplifying access and encouraging wider reuse of datasets across the heritage science community. File Access Requests will remain in place only for special cases, such as custom requests or access to alternative file formats. Licensing conditions and terms of use remain unchanged.

FTIR peak curation completed

FTIR peak curation has now been completed for all FTIR spectra currently available in the INFRA-ART database. Users can perform peak-based searches across the entire FTIR collection, enabling more targeted exploration of spectral data and supporting advanced analytical workflows.

Sample image previews

Each sample page now includes a small preview image, providing a quick visual indication of the sample's color and appearance alongside its analytical data. Preview images are currently available for about 50% of the samples, with additional images to be added progressively over the coming months as we continue processing the collection.

Cadmium Red (light)

Sample information

Sample ID

PK21120

Origin

Artificial

Chemical information

Cadmium sulfide (CdS) + cadmium selenide (CdSe) in varying proportion

Sample type

Reference material

Description

Powder sample (0–120 μ)

History of use

Starting with 1910

Sample source

Kremer Pigments

Alternative names

C.I. Pigment Red 108, PR108

Material class

Inorganic pigments, synthetic

Collaboration with Wiley Science Solutions

Following a recent collaboration agreement with Wiley Science Solutions, INFRA-ART reference spectra have been incorporated into the latest expansion of the [KnowItAll IR Spectral Library Collection](#). The new ATR-IR Pigments & Dyes collection includes more than 400 spectra from the INFRA-ART Spectral Library, expanding access to high-quality reference data for the analysis of pigments and dyes and supporting the needs of the scientific and heritage science communities. We look forward to continuing this collaboration and contributing additional high-quality reference datasets that support research, conservation, and material identification across a wide range of scientific and cultural heritage applications.

WILEY

Spectral Databases

From the leader in spectral data

ATR-IR - Pigments & Dyes - Wiley

Spectra – 420

Applications

- Art conservation
- Environmental and forensic analysis
- Degradation and alteration studies
- Forgery detection

New publication: INFRA-ART data service FAIRification

Article

From FAIR Principles to Practice: A Case Study of FAIRification in a Heritage Science Data Service

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Abstract

The FAIR principles have become a central framework for research data management and digital infrastructures, yet their implementation remains challenging within the long-tail of research. This paper examines how FAIR principles can be operationalized in practice through a case study on the FAIRification of the INFRA-ART Spectral Library, a specialized heritage science data service hosting multi-analytical spectral datasets related to art and archaeological materials. The FAIRification process was approached as an iterative and incremental workflow structured around three interconnected dimensions: technical interoperability, semantic alignment, and governance-oriented stewardship practices. Implementation activities included machine-actionable metadata exposure, semantic enrichment through ontology mappings and controlled vocabularies, interoperability-oriented infrastructure development, and the adoption of TRUST-aligned governance mechanisms. The results demonstrate substantial improvements in metadata quality, discoverability, interoperability, and repository transparency. At the same time, the FAIRification process highlighted persistent challenges related to fragmented semantic resources, evolving interoperability requirements, limited stewardship capacity, and dependence on project-based funding and institutional support. The study argues that effective FAIRification in long-tail data services depends on context-sensitive and incremental implementation approaches rather than rigid compliance models.

Keywords: FAIRification; data service; interoperability; TRUST principles; long-tail research; heritage science

An important milestone in the FAIR journey of the INFRA-ART data service has been reached with the publication of our FAIRification case study in *Heritage* (Special Issue: Advances in Digital Heritage Preservation and Open Science). The paper presents a roadmap-driven FAIRification approach aligned with the EOSC Interoperability Framework and complemented by the TRUST Principles, offering practical insights for implementing FAIR practices in research data services.

Towards CoreTrustSeal certification

The INFRA-ART data service has been accepted as a Candidate Member of the World Data System (WDS), marking an important milestone on our path towards CoreTrustSeal certification. This recognition reflects our ongoing commitment to open science, trustworthy data stewardship, and the long-term preservation and sharing of heritage science data. Through the WDS community, we look forward to strengthening international collaborations and contributing to more open and sustainable research data practices.

Trustworthy
Repository
Certified by

From the INFRA-ART Blog

Lessons learned from implementing FAIR principles in a long-tail heritage science data service

→ Drawing on the FAIRification of the INFRA-ART Spectral Library, this article reflects on the practical challenges of implementing FAIR principles in a small, long-tail heritage science data service and underscores the importance of long-term stewardship. [Read more](#)

From printed catalogues to digital spectral databases: the evolution of infrared spectral libraries

→ Tracing the evolution of infrared spectral libraries from print to digital databases, this article examines advances in spectral data management and ongoing efforts to improve access to resources for cultural heritage and conservation science. [Read more](#)

A guide to the pigment Colour Index: history and practical insights

→ Exploring the evolution of the Colour Index, the global standard for classifying pigments and dyes, this article examines its role in material identification and highlights how CI codes support research, conservation, and the study of colorants. [Read more](#)

Participation in OSPARK Bootcamp

Between March and April, members of the INFRA-ART team participated in the first [OSPARK Bootcamp](#), organised by the Digital Research Academy and OLS (Open Life Science). The multi-week programme was designed to strengthen communication and outreach skills within the Open Science community, helping research infrastructures and initiatives increase their visibility, engage more effectively with their audiences, and communicate the value of their services and resources. For INFRA-ART, the bootcamp provided a valuable opportunity to further develop how we communicate our mission,

promote our services, and engage with the heritage science community, while connecting with a wider network of Open Science advocates and research infrastructures.

Open Science on the Menu

OSPARK Bootcamp

Today's Specials

Outreach

Storytelling

Research Impact

Community Engagement

Open Research

Stay connected

Thank you for reading this edition of the INFRA-ART newsletter.

We welcome your feedback, suggestions, and collaboration ideas as we continue to expand and improve the INFRA-ART data service. Until our next issue, stay connected and be part of the INFRA-ART community:

 Visit the [INFRA-ART platform](#) regularly to discover our latest collections and services

- [Subscribe to our newsletter](#) and share it with colleagues who may find it useful
- Follow us on [LinkedIn](#) for real-time updates, news, and project developments
- Explore our open resources on [Zenodo](#)
- Contact us at info@infra-art.eu

 FIDELIS

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REGISTRY OF RESEARCH DATA REPOSITORIES

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standards, databases, policies

 OpenDOAR
